

Simplified Coherent Receiver for Zero-Touch Wireless Integration in Power-Splitting ODN with >40 dB Budget

Dinka Milovančev(1), Nemanja Vokić(1), Fotini Karinou(2), and Bernhard Schrenk(1)

(1) AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Center for Digital Safety&Security / Security & Communication Technologies, 1210 Vienna, Austria.

(2) Microsoft Research Ltd., 21 Station Road, Cambridge CB1 2FB, United Kingdom

Abstract

We experimentally demonstrate radio-over-fiber transmission over an optical budget of 42dB, using an ultra-low complexity, DSP-free coherent EML+TIA receiver. Its sensitivity enables the wireless integration in filterless, power-splitting wireline networks with budgets beyond NG-PON2 class-E2.

1) Introduction

Cloud-based radio and mobile fronthauling have become cornerstones of modern radio networks. The question whether antenna remoting is conducted in the digital or analogue optical domain has been subject to extensive discussion during recent years and has led to functional split definitions [1]. Among these, purely analogue radio-over-fiber transmission has sparked interest in conjunction with higher mm-wave radio frequencies [2, 3], where wide radio bandwidths and carrier aggregation apply. Analogue schemes contribute through simplification of remote radio head (RRH) equipment and thus reduce the cost and energy consumption of the field-distributed installations.

However, analogue radio-over-fiber schemes quickly face limitations due to distortions and noise. As a possible solution to extend the optical budget, we have earlier proposed the adoption of coherent detection at the RRH unit [4]. Though phase-sensitive, fully-coherent detection would bear a great potential to unlock high data rates required for digitized radio, it is bound to an increased component count and the complexity of digital signal processing (DSP) [5]. Instead, an analogue and technologically lean scheme based on an electro-absorption modulated laser (EML) has been adopted and found to preserve the radio signal integrity without the use of DSP resources [4].

This work extends our previous study on simplified coherent reception, through advancement of the homodyne detector enabled by a custom transimpedance amplifier (TIA) assembly, which, to our best knowledge, is the first coherent scheme based on EML+TIA receiver. We experimentally demonstrate the DSP-free downlink OFDM radio-over-fiber transmission. We obtain a convenient power margin of >6 dB for an extended budget of 35 dB, as it applies for wired power-splitting optical distribution networks (ODN) such as standardized through NG-PON2.

II) Wireless Integration in Brownfield ODNs of Wireline Networks

The roll-out of mobile fronthaul networks leverages the WDM dimension to enable virtual point-to-point links between the central office (CO) and the RRHs. However, the absence of WDM-centric architectures in the evolution of passive optical networks necessitates the modification of field-deployed splitter components for this purpose, or the deployment of new fiber. Both aspects do not bode well with a zero-touch migration of brownfield ODN. Towards the direction of wireline-wireless integration, we instead propose the adoption of DSP-free coherent homodyne detection to overcome extended optical budgets of filterless, power-splitting ODNs (Fig. 1). We address techno-economic roadblocks by relying on ultra-low complexity receivers. The simplified coherent receiver builds on an EML that exploits its distributed feedback (DFB) laser as injection-locked local oscillator (LO) to accomplish homodyne detection. This ensures that the radio signal integrity is preserved [4]. The monolithically integrated electro-absorption modulator (EAM) serves as photodiode that is tightly coupled to an electrical front-end. Up to now this front-end had been realized using a 50 Ω low-noise amplifier. Here, we use, for the first time, a TIA-based front-end (Fig. 1). It shall be stressed that full-duplex operation for this EML-driven coherent receiver, though feasible in principle [6], is not the focus of this downlink-oriented work.

Fig. 1. Zero-touch wireless integration in wired brownfield ODN and coherent EML+TIA receiver.

III) Experimental Setup for the Coherent Optical Mobile Fronthaul

The EML+TIA receiver was evaluated in the experimental arrangement shown in Fig. 2a. An arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) drives an optical inphase/quadrature (I/Q) modulator with a clipped OFDM signal. The OFDM signal at 3.5 GHz had 128 sub-carriers over a bandwidth of 125 MHz. The signal is electro-optically modulated at 1298.8 nm as a double-sideband signal. The I/Q modulator allows to set the optical carrier-to-signal power ratio (oCSPR). The radio-over-fiber signal is boosted by a semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA) and is launched with 6 dBm at an OSNR of 25.7 dB/0.1nm. In addition, four modulated channels at 1295.3, 1309.3, 1309.9 and 1323.3 nm have been appended to form an optical multi-channel feed with uniform power level (Fig. 2b). The ITU-T G.652B compatible feeder fiber of the ODN had a length of 28.6 km. A variable attenuator (A_{tt}) emulates the distribution split. A 250 m long drop fiber connects to the RRH site. Reception at the RRH is accomplished through the EML, which served as single-ended, single-polarization coherent homodyne detector with integrated LO. A polarization controller (PC) was used to account for polarization-dependent operation; however, polarization-independent detection has been demonstrated earlier through use of a diversity receiver scheme [7].

The EML-TIA assembly built on bondable components (Fig. 1) in order to minimize parasitic capacitances at the device interfaces. The photocurrent generated in the EAM was amplified and converted to a voltage signal matched for a 50Ω system. Because of its large dc component, the chip-on-carrier EML and the TIA were ac-coupled capacitively. The EAM bias line consisted of a series inductor with a dc-branch of a wideband discrete bias-T.

The EML is locked to the residual optical carrier of the incident radio-over-fiber signal, leading to homodyne detection. For this purpose the EAM and the DFB sections are biased at -0.75V and ~90 mA, respectively. These bias points relate to an EAM that acts as semi-transparent photodiode and a LO that is fine tuned to ensure stable locking while it operates close to its maximum output power. The received OFDM signal is then digitized by a real-time oscilloscope in order to estimate the error vector magnitude (EVM) after signal transmission.

A drawback of the available TIA used in this work is seen in its low linearity at higher input signals, especially under coherent detection where the upper limit for linear operation of the fixed-gain circuit is already reached at a moderate optical input power level. Nonlinear distortions, however, do not bode well with multi-carrier signals such as the OFDM-based radio. For this reason, we have additionally investigated the EVM improvement through a DSP-assisted non-linear signal-signal beat interference estimation with subsequent digital cancellation, similar as in [8].

Fig. 2. (a) Experimental setup for the coherent optical mobile fronthaul.
(b) Transmitted O-band spectrum at the output of the SOA booster.

IV) Characterization of the Low-Complexity Coherent Receiver at the RRH

Figure 3a reports the VLI characteristics of the O-band EML. It features a low threshold current of 13 mA and reaches a fiber-coupled power of 7.9 dBm for a DFB current of 100 mA for a fully transparent EAM section. The side-mode suppression ratio was 50.9 dB and the relative intensity noise (RIN) of this DFB-based LO reached a value of -157 dB/Hz at the relaxation oscillation peak. As we will prove,

this low value will enable a sufficiently high signal-to-noise ratio after single-ended coherent detection, which in contrary to balanced detectors cannot suppress RIN in the same way. Tunability of the LO was accomplished through DFB current or temperature adjustment at 2.26 GHz/mA and 11.8 GHz/°C, respectively. The EAM section of the EML reaches a light extinction of 25.6 dB for a reverse bias of 2.5V and has a peak extinction of 14.7 dB/V_{pp} when being used as loss modulator.

The measured EML+TIA reception bandwidth was 6.1 GHz, which is below the 10G rating of the TIA. This is explained by the additional parasitic components of the ac-coupling that was required to reject the large dc component of the photocurrent. However, this opto-electronic bandwidth covers very well the bandwidth that is required to optically feed analogue wideband radio at an intermediate carrier frequency to a RRH, where it is subsequently up-converted to the final radio carrier frequency.

V) Transmission Performance and Compatible Optical Budget

We evaluated OFDM transmission for QPSK and 16-QAM sub-carriers in terms of EVM performance. The oCSPR was chosen with -7 dB, meaning that the optical carrier is highly suppressed as it solely serves the purpose of receiver locking, which can be achieved at very low power levels [9, 10]. The received signal spectra after detection at the RRH are presented in Fig. 3b for coherent detection with activated LO (i.e., DFB section of the EML) and for direct detection with dark LO. As the spectra confirm, there are no direct-detection terms above the noise floor for the typically low received optical power levels in the range of -35 dBm.

The EVM performance is reported in Fig. 3c for single- (λ_2, \triangle) and multi-channel transmission ($\lambda_1 \dots \lambda_5, \bullet$) with optically isolated receiver. For the single-channel transmission at the target wavelength λ_2 , we obtained a reception sensitivity of -36.1 dBm (\triangle) at the EVM limit of 12.5%. Together with the signal launch of the transmitter, this corresponds to an optical budget of 42.1 dB, which is sufficiently large to absorb the O-band fiber transmission loss at the feeder and a 1:128 splitting loss. After erosion of these basic contributions, a large power margin of 12.8 dB remains. Two limits apply for the signal reception, which are given by the noise limit for lower received power levels, and by the non-linear limit due to receiver saturation towards higher received levels of -32 dBm and above. In case that DSP-assisted non-linear mitigation is employed, the EVM improves by 5.1% at a power of -28.5 dBm.

The co-propagation of the four adjacent channels did not lead a penalty towards the noise limit but shows the susceptibility of the receiver towards higher received power. The EVM starts to rise sharper and earlier, at an about 2.5 dB lower signal power. This penalty is attributed to the single-ended receiver architecture and its missing common-mode rejection property. The received 16QAM-OFDM constellation is presented as inset in Fig. 3c.

In order to compare against a more realistic deployment scenario, where the coherent receiver is directly connected to the drop fiber and thus being exposed to optical feedback effects at high optical budgets, the single-channel performance has been also investigated for this non-isolated case (\square) by removing the optical circulator in front of the EML+TIA receiver. We did not find a penalty with respect to the optically isolated case.

Fig. 3. (a) VLI characteristics of the EML's LO. (b) Received signal spectra. (c) EVM performance for single- and multi-channel transmission.

VI) Conclusions

We have experimentally demonstrated, for the first time, a coherent EML+TIA receiver for DSP-free radio-over-fiber transmission. The reception sensitivity below -36 dBm for single-carrier, 125-MHz OFDM radio enables the zero-touch integration of wireline networks in filterless, brownfield ODNs of wireline access architectures, leaving a convenient 6-dB margin for the extended class-E2 (35 dB) budget of NG-PON2. Linearization of the receiver and a balanced detector scheme for the suppression of common-mode noise are left for further study.

VII) References

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